

CLINICOPATHOLOGICAL CONFERENCE: AN ELDERLY MAN WITH ERYTHEMA INDURATUM

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Case Report

A 72-year-old man was admitted into the Department of Geriatrics for a 2-week history of painful skin nodules over both legs. He had been regularly followed up in our specialist out-patient clinic for ischaemic heart disease and paroxysmal atrial tachycardia, and was maintained on verapamil 40mg bd, isosorbide dinitrate 40mg bd and sublingual glycerol trinitrate prn.

One and a half months ago he was admitted for a few days into a private hospital because of fever and anal pain, and was found to have perianal abscess. He was treated with incision and drainage, with excision of the associated sinus tract. Biopsy of the perianal abscess was diagnosed as "marked acute and chronic inflammation." In the report, the lesion was described as "multiple pieces of granulation tissue infiltrated by numerous acute and chronic inflammatory cells in which foreign body giant cells are also seen. Granulomatous inflammation characteristic of tuberculosis and Crohn's disease are not demonstrated. Also present are several small pieces of squamous epithelium with markedly dilated submucosal blood vessels consistent with haemorrhoid. One small piece of skin contains granulation tissue with acute and chronic inflammation deep in the dermis and the subcutaneous fat."

Post-operatively, he still had subjective feverishness with a flu-like illness and dysuria. He had a weight loss of 6kg since the operation. Two weeks prior to admission to our hospital he had also been treated by a private practitioner with penicillin, potassium permanganate bath, steroid & neomycin cream, and chlorpheniramine (piriton). He had history of urticaria after mefenamic acid (ponstan) one year ago.

In the past, the patient had history of a lung shadow detected by chest X-ray at the age of 20 and had been treated with drugs for 3 months. The exact diagnosis of the lung lesion was not known. Lung shadow was again detected at the age of 46 during a pre-employment check up, and thereafter he had yearly chest X-rays until he retired from the government at 57. At the age of 65, he had one episode of blood-streaked sputum. Chest X-ray then was reported as "pleural thickening in both apices, with small multiple calcified foci in left apex, small area of patchy consolidation in right costophrenic angle." He was then treated with one course of amoxicillin with improvement. One week before this admission, he coughed up a few

mouthfuls of fresh blood during a morning walk. He had been a chronic smoker since the age of around 20 but quitted smoking 7 years ago on medical advice. He had mild cough for years and there was no recent increase in cough or any constitutional upset. He also had right inguinal hernia for the past 3 months. He was living with his family members and was unaware of any previous contact with tuberculosis.

Examination revealed an afebrile patient in good condition, with no lymphadenopathy nor abnormal chest signs. Tender erythematous nodular eruptions without ulcerations were found over both the anterior and posterior aspects of both legs (Figures 1,2,3). Erythema induratum was diagnosed for the skin lesion. Although drug-induced erythema nodosum had been considered as an alternative diagnosis in view of the history of drug allergy and the recent exposure to multiple medication, this was considered less likely since the nodular eruptions were found on the posterior aspects of legs as well.

Investigations revealed calcified granulomata in the apex of left lung on the chest X-ray (Figure 4), haemoglobin of 13.2g/dl, white cell count of $7.2 \times 10^9/l$ (N57%, L31.1%), ESR of 69mm/hr and a normal clotting profile. Mid-stream urine revealed no pus cells nor grew any organisms. The tuberculin test was positive.

A clinical diagnosis of active pulmonary tuberculosis with erythema induratum was made. This was confirmed by the presence of acid-alcohol-fast bacilli on all three direct sputum smears. The diagnosis of erythema induratum was supported by the histopathological findings of the skin biopsy taken from the nodular skin lesions, which showed a mixed inflammatory cellular infiltrate in the subcutaneous fat lobules (Figure 5). Epithelioid cell granulomas were found scattered around the biopsy, and in a few foci, there were Langhan's multinucleate giant cells (Figure 6). Tissue necrosis, though not "caseating", was seen in the subcutaneous fat. Some of the large and medium size vessels had inflammatory infiltration in their walls. Ziehl-Neelsen stain for acid-fast bacilli was negative.

On the second day of admission, the patient had frank haemoptysis. On the fifth day, there was a small kick of fever up to 37.7°C at 8pm (but ice-bag had been given). He was started on anti-tuberculosis drugs (isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide). The fever subsided and the erythema induratum over the legs gradually resolved when followed

Figure 1. Anterior aspects of both legs showing nodular eruptions.

Figure 2. Posterior aspects of both legs showing nodular eruptions.

Figure 4. Chest X-ray showing calcified granulomata in the apex of left lung.

Figure 3. Close-up view of nodular eruptions.

up at the out-patient specialist clinic (Figure 7). His body weight increased by 4kg in the past 7 months. The sputum culture result later returned as growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* sensitive to gentamycin, isoniazid and rifampicin.

Discussion

Erythema induratum is a chronic granulomatous inflammation of the subcutis most commonly affecting the legs in patients with tuberculosis. It is a form of lobular panniculitis with vasculitis known as nodular vasculitis, which is an inflammatory disorder of the subcutaneous fat associated with prominent large-vessel vasculitis¹. The lesion probably represents a hypersensitivity reaction to various stimuli with primary injury on vessel walls². Various drugs and bacterial infections have been implicated as initiating factors, but the aetiology remains unclear in the majority. Some authorities identify erythema induratum (Bazin's disease) as a distinct entity of nodular vasculitis with a tuberculous aetiology. A study of three patients with subcutaneous erythematous nodules in different phases of development, nonspecific systemic symptoms and positive tuberculin test suggested that the mycobacterium has a vascular tropism and may cause a primary granulomatous arteritis³.

In 1861, Bazin first described the typical skin changes associated with tuberculosis. Proven cases of tuberculous erythema induratum are said to be exceedingly rare in the

Figure 5. Low power photomicrograph of the skin biopsy showing extensive inflammatory infiltration in the subcutaneous fat lobules.

Figure 6. High power photomicrograph of the skin biopsy showing that the inflammatory infiltrate consists of epithelioid histiocytes and multinucleate giant cells of the Langhan type (arrowheads).

United States⁴, and one recent case report in the United States was in a Chinese woman⁵. However, it is not that

Figure 7. Posterior aspects of both legs after anti-tuberculosis treatment.

uncommon in Hong Kong. Locally, erythema induratum is one of the two commonest forms of cutaneous tuberculosis, which accounted for 0.3% of new skin cases in 1982⁶. Rademaker et al.¹ reported 26 cases of erythema induratum in the United Kingdom and noticed that three fourths were of Anglo-Saxon origin. They emphasized that erythema induratum is not rare and is frequently misdiagnosed as is evidenced by the long history of clinical presentation with a mean duration of 4.8 years (range 1 month to 16 years).

The classical clinical description of erythema induratum is "chronic tender, erythematous nodules or plaques over the posterolateral legs most commonly in middle aged woman"². However, our case is an elderly male and the lesions are present on both the anterior as well as posterior aspects of legs. In Rademaker's series¹ of 26 patients with erythema induratum, 19% were aged 65 or over with the oldest being a 74-year-old man; and though most of the lesions were present on the legs, they also occurred on the arms, thighs, feet and buttocks.

The clinical significance of erythema induratum is that it leads to search for a source of active tuberculosis. This is particularly important when respiratory symptoms are minimal or absent so that the diagnosis of tuberculosis might not be suspected (see the appendix). For this elderly man, it is likely that he had acquired the tuberculosis infection at the age of 20 or earlier. The infection which has been held in check, "breaks out" as cell mediated immune responses decline with ageing⁷. The present episode of illness is a reactivation of dormant foci in the left lung apex. Though he did not notice any recent increase in cough, the presence of hernia for the past 3 months might reflect an intermittent increase in intra-abdominal pressure secondary to significant cough.

Although there is no histological granulomatous inflammation characteristic of tuberculosis in the perianal abscess biopsy, the close temporal sequence, the persistence of post-operative fever (though intermittent), the significant weight loss dated back from the operation, and the

presence of giant cells in the perianal biopsy might lead one to speculate whether he had anal tuberculosis (either direct tuberculous infection⁸ or erythema induratum involving the perianal skin) as part of the same illness. Rademaker et al.¹ have emphasized the difficulty in assessing the histopathological changes in erythema induratum because the histological appearances vary greatly with the age of the lesion examined. In their series, granulomas were absent in almost one third of the cases and when present were mostly small, noncaseating, poorly circumscribed, and composed of epithelioid histiocytes with occasional Langhans' and foreign body-type multinucleate giant cells.

Regarding the aetiology of ischaemic heart disease and paroxysmal atrial tachycardia in this man, it would be interesting to speculate whether he had myocardial tuberculosis. Being a chronic smoker, he was of course at risk of developing coronary artery disease. However, his chest pain showed no relationship to exertion and coronary angiogram revealed normal coronary vessels so that he had been labeled as suffering from a coronary vasospastic disorder. There have been case reports of myocardial tuberculosis presenting as cardiac arrhythmia (supraventricular or ventricular), retrosternal chest pain or sudden death; but the tuberculosis aetiology in those reports was diagnosed only after death at post-mortem examination⁹.

Both the lung and the skin lesions of this elderly man responded well to anti-tuberculosis treatment, just like the case reported by Hassoun⁵. In Rademaker's series¹, all the 26 patients with erythema induratum responded to anti-tuberculous therapy. However, relapses (8 out of 17) occurred in those treated with single (isoniazid) or two (isoniazid, rifampicin) drugs whereas none of the 9 patients treated with triple therapy (isoniazid, rifampicin, ethambutol) had relapse. Thus, they recommended treating patients with erythema induratum with a full course of anti-tuberculous drugs.

Appendix: "undiagnosed" erythema induratum (Dr. T. K. Kong)

I searched through my faintest memory back to childhood and discovered that I have seen similar skin lesions (erythema induratum) before. That occurred in my mother when I was just 11 years old. She was unwell since the age of 44. She started off with ankle pain and was treated as "rheumatism" at an out-patient clinic with anti-rheumatic injections, which I guess were steroids since she got mooning and plethora of face with such treatment. She had some symptomatic relief of the ankle pain with the injections but the pain recurred once the injections were stopped. Then she got mid-night shivering. This was followed by tender reddish chilblain-like nodules over both the anterior and postero-lateral aspects of her legs, for which she had sought multiple doctors without improvement. She finally settled on a herbalist, who advised my mother regular hot baths of her legs with herbs. The leg nodules gradually resolved after one year. She then had menorrhagia and was treated

with dilatation and curettage. Soon after that, she got profuse night-sweating, palpitation, and fleeting pain over fingers and shoulders and night cramps. The rheumatic symptoms were worse at night and in cold windy weather, and she was intolerant of air-conditioning. The symptoms were so distressing that she couldn't sleep well. She rested herself in bed most of the time and was so weak that she could not go out marketing, a task which had been taken over by me. She again consulted multiple doctors but there was no improvement. The medical expenses consumed were so much that for the first time my family was in debt. Since the night sweat was tasteless (not salty), she treated herself with salt water and some herbal remedies. She also took herbs prescribed from a neighbour. Her illness finally subsided by the age of 48. At 54 (I was then a preclinical medical student), my mother noticed a hard right cervical lump. She was seen by a surgeon and the provisional diagnosis was malignant cervical lymph node. Open cervical lymph node biopsy was done and to my relief, the histological report was just "chronic non-specific inflammation." However she had persistent discharge from the biopsy wound site, for which she was treated with local dressing. At one of the surgical follow-ups, a surgeon sent a wound swab for acid-fast bacilli, which was found to be positive. The diagnosis of tuberculous cervical lymphadenitis was finally made 6 months after the lymph node biopsy. My mother was then treated with anti-tuberculous drugs and the wound healed completely. She is now healthy and is free from any rheumatic symptoms. In retrospect, she got tuberculosis with erythema induratum earlier at the age of 44, and was activated by steroid. This retrospective diagnosis of erythema induratum was "confirmed" by showing the clinical photos of the legs of the elderly man of the present case to my mother - she immediately recognized the lesions! The night shivering and sweating were features of nocturnal fever characteristic of tuberculosis. She probably had tuberculous rheumatism^{10,11}, a disease said to be more common among Asians¹². At no time did she complain of any chronic cough. She was not aware of any contact history of tuberculosis. However, at the age of 30, my mother took care of my grandmother during her terminal illness. I traced my grandmother's death certificate from my father and discovered that the cause of death of my grandmother was tuberculous meningitis, which was unfortunately not revealed to my parents.

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References

1. Rademaker M, Lowe DG, Munro DD. Erythema induratum (Bazin's disease). *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1989;21:740-745.
2. Sams WM, Lynch PJ (eds). Principles and practice of dermatology. New York: Churchill Livingstone, 1990:490-492.
3. Rodrigues CJ, de Campos FP, Furtado-Mendonca LL, et al. Mycobacterial subcutaneous arteritis. *Rev Inst Med Trop Sao Paulo (Brazil)* 1990;32:346-350.
4. Pillsbury DM, Shelly WB, Kilgman AM (eds). *Dermatology*. Philadelphia: Saunders, 1968:527.
5. Hassoun PM, Shepherd KE, Flotte TJ, et al. Erythema induratum and active pulmonary tuberculosis. *Am J Med* 1988;84:784-785.
6. Wong KO. Skin disease in Hong Kong. *Therapaeia* 1983 (Nov):8.
7. Fox RA. The clinical response to infection. In Fox RA (ed). *Immunology & infection in the elderly*. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone, 1984:17.
8. Seow-Choen F, Hay AJ, Heard S, Phillips RK. Bacteriology of anal fistulae. *Br J Surg* 1992;79:27-28.
9. Behr G, Palin HC, Temperley JM. Myocardial tuberculosis. *Br Med J* 1977;i:951.
10. Isaacs AJ, Sturrock RD. Poncet's disease - fact or fiction? A re-appraisal of tuberculous rheumatism. *Tubercle* 1974;55:135-142.
11. Pasternack MS, Mark EJ. Case records of the Massachusetts General Hospital - a 51-year old Ethiopian woman with myalgia, weight loss, and mediastinal lymphadenopathy. *New Engl J Med* 1993;328:195-202.
12. Allen SC. Ageing and the respiratory system. In: Brocklehurst JC, Tallis RC, Fillett H (eds). *Textbook of Geriatric Medicine and Gerontology* 4th edn. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone, 1992:739-768.

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